

AUSTRALIAN EARTH SYSTEM SIMULATOR

WORK PLAN 2023-2024

ACCESS-NRI Annual Work Plan

FY 2023-2024

Summary

The ACCESS-NRI Annual Work Plan summarises the major bodies of work across the organisation for the remainder of the 2023-2024 financial year. It is intended to provide transparency and to promote feedback and discussion with the ACCESS community that we are here to support.

The 2023-2024 workplan provides project details under 4 broad focus areas:

- Model Development
- Model Releases & Infrastructure
- Software & Data
- Training & Engagement

The projects in each area are broadly ordered by priority.

Model Development

Project	Description	Lead and team(s) involved	Effort*
CABLE maintainability and improvements	Work on testing and code design to improve the maintainability of CABLE. This includes migrating CABLE to Github and implementing continuous integration (CI).	Claire Carouge <i>Land Surface Model Team</i>	< 1FTE
ACCESS-AM3 development	Development of ACCESS-AM3 configuration and user documentation. This includes coupling of CABLE3 to the UM GA9 configuration (vn 13).	Claire Carouge <i>Land Surface Model Team Atmosphere Model Team CSIRO</i>	>2 FTE
ACCESS-OM3 development	Development and beta release of the ACCESS-OM3 configuration (based on MOM6 and CICE6 with NUOPC coupling). This also includes the WOMBAT BGC model.	Andy Hogg and Andrew Kiss (ANU) <i>Ocean Model Team COSIMA</i>	>2 FTE
ACCESS-ESM3 development	Development of ACCESS-ESM3 configuration and user documentation. This includes coupling of the UM to ACCESS-OM3 with NUOPC and adding new land use change capability to the coupled version of CABLE. This model is targeted for use in an Australian contribution to CMIP7.	Martin Dix <i>Atmosphere Model Team Ocean Model Team Land Surface Model Team CSIRO</i>	>2 FTE
Model optimisation	Determine and document optimised load balance and IO configurations for ACCESS-CM2 and ACCESS-ESM1.5.	Martin Dix <i>Atmosphere Model Team</i>	< 1FTE
Ancillary suites and tools	Develop suites for standard present-day configurations and tools for working with non-standard configurations (e.g., paleo).	Heidi Nettelbeck <i>Atmosphere Model Team</i>	1–2 FTE
UM/JULES maintenance	Maintaining UM and JULES rose stem testing. Assisting users with Met Office ticket approval process. Work relating to NCI's transition from accessdev.	Martin Dix <i>Atmosphere Model Team</i>	< 1FTE
Ice sheet modelling and coastal modelling commons	Recruit team to establish ACCESS-NRI capability in ice sheet and coastal modelling as part of the NCRIS-wide Coastal Research Infrastructure (CoastRI) Initiative.	Andy Hogg	1–2 FTE

*Full time equivalent (FTE) staff needed to scope, undertake, and deliver activity.

Model Releases & Infrastructure

Project	Description	Lead and team(s)	Effort*
Support for legacy configurations	<p>Ensure users can continue to run existing configurations. Work includes compiling, updating and enhancing existing user documentation for the 5 ACCESS-NRI supported configurations.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ACCESS-OM2 • ACCESS-ESM1.5 • ACCESS-CM2 • AUS2200 • ACCESS-AM3 	<p>Heidi Nettelbeck</p> <p><i>Atmosphere Model Team CSIRO Bureau of Meteorology</i></p>	1–2 FTE
Model release pipeline	<p>New pipeline to build, test and deploy all ACCESS-NRI models in future, improving efficiency, reliability and reproducibility. This includes enabling continuous integration and deployment (CI/CD) and managing model component software and dependencies with Spack, a build-from-source package manager. All DevOps pipelines are configured and run from GitHub, so they are open and discoverable, including software deployments at NCI.</p>	<p>Aidan Heerdegen</p> <p><i>Model Release Team</i></p>	>2 FTE
Flagship releases	<p>Work to prepare, build and deploy the first ‘flagship’ release through the new release pipeline for each ACCESS-NRI supported configuration. Scheduled releases for this FY include:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ACCESS-OM2 • ACCESS-ESM1.5 • ACCESS-CM2 • AUS2200 • ACCESS-AM3 	<p>Aidan Heerdegen</p> <p><i>Model Release Team</i></p>	>2 FTE
Impact tracking	<p>Initial framework for tracking uptake and impact of ACCESS-NRI infrastructure on the national and international research community.</p>	<p>Kelsey Druken Aidan Heerdegen Natalia Bateman</p> <p><i>Model Release Team Training & Engagement Team</i></p>	1–2 FTE

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Software & Data

Project	Description	Lead and team(s)	Effort*
Model evaluation & diagnostics tools	<p>Building a standardised, reproducible framework for evaluation of ACCESS outputs, including a semi-automated pipeline for a CMIP7 ACCESS submission. Tools and workflows to be released include:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ESMValTool workflow • ILAMB workflow • CABLE evaluation framework • ACCESS-NRI MED Live Diagnostics tool 	<p>Romain Beucher</p> <p><i>Model Evaluation & Diagnostics Team Land Surface Model Team</i></p>	>2 FTE
Data visualisation	<p>Create high-impact visualisations to help explain the ACCESS models, data outputs and science across the community. Open access to the visualisation code and tools (wherever possible) as well as visualisation training will also be outputs of this work.</p>	<p>Owen Kaluza</p> <p><i>Model Evaluation & Diagnostics Team Training & Engagement Team</i></p>	1–2 FTE
MED Portal	<p>Community space to collect, curate and share evaluation recipes and diagnostics. This work also includes enabling continuous integration and deployment (CI/CD) for COSIMA recipes to support ACCESS-OM3 development.</p>	<p>Romain Beucher</p> <p><i>Model Evaluation & Diagnostics Team</i></p>	1–2 FTE
Data releases and data management	<p>Release and data management of ACCESS model outputs and related datasets (including merit-based datasets nominated by the Community Working Groups). This work includes the release and support of the ACCESS-NRI Intake tool, which enables the cataloguing and discovery of ACCESS data at NCI as well as integration with the NCI Data Collections (and NCI cataloguing tools).</p>	<p>Romain Beucher Kelsey Druken</p> <p><i>Model Evaluation & Diagnostics Team ACCESS-NRI Working Group Liaisons</i></p>	< 1FTE
Improved observational constraint and testing facility for ACCESS-NRI land models	<p>This project aims to build a standardisation pipeline for TERN ecosystem data, and the automated testing infrastructure to utilise TERN data streams, to better constrain development and simulation of ACCESS-NRI supported land models.</p>	<p>Gab Abramowitz (UNSW) Claire Carouge Romain Beucher</p> <p><i>Land Surface Model Team Model Evaluation & Diagnostics Team</i></p>	1–2 FTE
Software Transformation	<p>Establish a new Software Transformation Team to bring the specialist software engineering skills required for the ACCESS modelling framework to take advantage of advances in computing hardware, and to position ACCESS for future changes in technology.</p>	<p>Kelsey Druken</p>	1–2 FTE

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Training & Engagement

Project	Description	Lead and team(s)	Effort*
2024 ACCESS Community Workshop	Host and support the annual ACCESS community workshop. Scheduled for September 2024 in Canberra.	Victoria Allen <i>Business Team</i>	>2 FTE
Supporting Community Working Groups	Support for the 6 Community Working Groups. This includes facilitating the two-way flow of information between each Working Group and ACCESS-NRI developers and enabling access to HPC resources (compute and storage) at NCI.	Claire Carouge, Martin Dix, Kelsey Druken, Aidan Heerdegen, Heidi Nettelbeck and Dougie Squire <i>ACCESS-NRI Working Group Liaisons</i>	1–2 FTE
Communication and outreach engagement	Communicating the impact and importance of ACCESS-NRI's software infrastructure and expertise for climate science researchers and decision-makers. This work includes ACCESS-NRI's regular newsletter (ACCESSStory), annual Highlights Report, online communication channels, impact stories, visualisations, media releases and outreach engagement activities.	Natalia Bateman <i>Training and Engagement Team</i>	1–2 FTE
ACCESS Training	Training events for new and existing users. The 2024 Community Workshop will be a major training event. Minor events will include support for hackathon-style events and webinar/information sessions, the majority being targeted at supported models, software and data releases.	Roger Edberg <i>Training and Engagement Team Model Development Teams (Atmosphere, Land, Ocean) Model Evaluation & Diagnostics Team Model Release</i>	1–2 FTE
ACCESS-Hive training catalogue	Establish a training section on the ACCESS-Hive user portal along with curated content related to released model configurations, tools and data. This will include user training examples, curated video content and a curated library of recommended content for core skills.	Roger Edberg <i>Training and Engagement Team</i>	1–2 FTE
Graduate-style program for PhD students	Work to scope options and approaches for a graduate-style internship program at ACCESS-NRI. The aim is to review existing programs and trial 1-2 students.	Kelsey Druken <i>Cross-organisation</i>	< 1FTE

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Acknowledgements

The ACCESS-NRI Annual Workplan was inspired and influenced by [Atlas of Living Australia's Annual Workplan](#):

Atlas of Living Australia (2023) Atlas of Living Australia Annual Workplan 2023-24, Atlas of Living Australia, Publication Series No. 7, Canberra, Australia, pp. 19. <https://doi.org/10.54102/ala.46036>

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